

Exploring Socioeconomic Influences on Higher Education Access in Uganda: Findings from the 2016-2017 National Household Survey.

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Abstract

This study investigates the socioeconomic determinants of access to higher education in Uganda, utilizing data from the Uganda National Household Survey of 2016/17. Despite global efforts to enhance educational equity, only 11% of Ugandans aged 22-25 have completed higher education, with stark disparities between urban and rural areas. Logistic regression analysis reveals that household wealth is a key determinant, with the wealthiest individuals being 13 percentage points more likely to access higher education. Parental education, urban residency, and regional location also significantly influence access. Contrary to common perceptions, the study finds that females are more likely to access higher education than males, particularly in rural areas. This research offers valuable insights into the socioeconomic barriers to higher education in Uganda, providing evidence for targeted policy interventions.

Introduction

Making quality education accessible to all is of great policy concern globally. Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) number four aims to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and lifelong learning opportunities for all. Goal 4.3 aims to ensure equal access for all people to affordable and quality technical, vocational, and tertiary education, including university (UN General Assembly, 2015).

Yet in Uganda, only 11% of the population aged 22-25 years have completed tertiary or higher education (Uganda Bureau of Statistics [UBOS], 2017). Moreover the number of students enrolled in Uganda's tertiary education level, regardless of age, as a percentage of the population of official school age (for the tertiary level) was only four per cent, which according to UBOS (2017) is below the Sub Saharan Africa average of six per cent and the global average of 26%. Besides low participation rates, enrolment is not equally distributed among sub-regions, rural and urban areas. For instance, tertiary-level enrolment was only 2.6% in rural areas as compared to 7.6% in urban areas. Among sub-regions, the central sub-region has an enrolment of 4.8% compared to Bunyoro with only 2% (UBOS, 2017).

Higher education is critical for Uganda's economic growth and development because it promotes accumulating productive skills and capabilities, generating new knowledge through innovation, and quicker adoption of existing innovative technologies (Breton, 2013; Holmes, 2013). Furthermore, higher education has the highest average returns among all education levels in Africa (Peet et al., 2015; Psacharopoulos & Patrinos, 2004). According to Psacharopoulos & Patrinos (2004), private returns to higher education are still increasing, and the highest returns to education are recorded in low and middle-income countries like Uganda. Besides, higher education has other considerable benefits to individuals and society such as lower crime rates, better health, democratization, reduced poverty, and civic engagement, among others (Brennan et al., 2013; McMahan, 2018, 2021; McMahan & Oketch, 2013).

The objective of this paper is to examine the socio-economic determinants of access to higher education in Uganda. I seek to understand the association between socioeconomic characteristics and the likelihood of an individual accessing higher education. In addition to socioeconomic characteristics at the individual and household level, I also examine the influence of community characteristics like access to the Internet, access to schools, and the location of the household (urban versus rural and region of Uganda in which it is located) on access to higher education.

To achieve the objective above, I use data from the Uganda National Household Survey of 2016/17 which is nationally representative and covers both the household socioeconomic variables and community characteristics needed for this study. I then run a logistic regression on a binary outcome, equal to one if an individual is enrolled or completed higher education and zero otherwise, and a set of socio-economic characteristics at the individual, household, and community levels as the independent variables. I run four other models on subsets of the data by location (rural and urban) and by gender (female and male). The aim was to examine whether the determinants of access to higher education vary according to location and gender.

I find that household wealth is a key determinant of access to higher education in Uganda. Specifically, individuals from households in the highest wealth quintile are 13 percentage points more likely to access higher education compared to those from households in the lowest wealth quintile. This underscores the significant role that financial resources play in facilitating access to higher education. Additionally, the study finds that each additional year of schooling attained by the household head is associated with a 1.5 percentage point increase in the likelihood of accessing higher education.

Furthermore, I find that location is a vital determinant of access to higher education, with individuals from urban areas 5 percentage points more likely to access higher education than those from rural areas. Similarly, individuals from western Uganda, where poverty levels are relatively low, are 5 percentage points more likely to access higher education as compared to northern Uganda with relatively high poverty levels. Contrary to earlier studies, I find evidence that suggests females are more likely to access higher education than males. In rural areas, males are 3 percentage points less likely to access higher education than females. Generally, the findings suggest that individuals in rural and under-developed regions of Uganda are disadvantaged in their pursuit of higher education.

This paper contributes to the literature on access to higher education in Uganda in the following ways. First, it uses a nationally representative sample to examine the socio-economic determinants of access to higher education in Uganda. Unlike previous studies which focused on a segment of higher education in Uganda, for example, females (Kwesiga, 1993), Makerere University (Jansson et al., 2017; Mayanja, 1998) or a few universities within Uganda (Nshemereirwe, 2016), this paper examines access to higher education for the entire Uganda. Therefore, results from this study are generalizable to the whole of Uganda.

Second, this paper explores the association of variables such as internet access which have not been examined in previous studies on access to higher education. In the digital era, with education transitioning to blended learning, exploring the influence of access to the internet on accessing higher education is worthwhile. Lastly, this paper provides suggestive evidence that females are more likely to access higher education than males in Uganda. Generally, within Uganda, the belief among policymakers is that females are disadvantaged in their pursuit of higher education, however, evidence from this study suggests the opposite. This study presents evidence that suggests females are generally more advantaged than males in accessing higher education.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: the next section discusses the conceptual framework, next is a discussion of the data and descriptive statistics. The empirical framework is presented next and this is followed by a presentation of the results and discussion, and finally, I present the Summary and concluding remarks.

Conceptual Framework

Higher education can be defined as, any of several types of education given in post-secondary institutions of learning and usually affording, at the end of a course of study, a named degree, diploma, or certificate of higher studies. Uganda also has post-primary education opportunities offered through tertiary institutions, which cover primary, lower secondary, and upper secondary leavers (Jacob et al., 2009). However, this study focuses on higher education offered after completion of lower and upper secondary education i.e., the Uganda Certificate of Education (UCE) and Uganda Advanced Certificate of Education (UACE). After UCE, students in Uganda can attend technical institutes for a minimum of three years after which they are awarded advanced certificates. To attend a diploma or degree program, one needs to have completed UACE and met the requirements of admission to such a program. Different programs have different minimum admission requirements. For this study, our definition of higher education will include those who have attended a course of study after completing UCE or UACE leading to the award of a degree, diploma, or advanced certificate of studies.

The determinants of demand and access to higher education can be categorized into two categories: individual determinants and institutional determinants. Ogawa & Imura (2010) citing the general report on individual demand for higher education by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) from 1978, propose that the individual and institutional determinants that influence the pursuit of higher education can further be divided into four groups. Individual determinants can further be divided into student characteristics which include aspects of gender, educational achievement, intellectual abilities, interests and aspirations; and personal environment which includes aspects of family background, school environment, and peer groups. Institutional determinants can further be subdivided into the educational system which looks at the curriculum, and the society the individual hails from that is the socio-cultural conditions and the economy including the private rates of returns to education.

Jimenez & Salas-velasco (2000) and Ogawa & Imura (2010) in their conceptual frameworks categorize the above determinants into objective determinants and subjective determinants. The objective determinants are family background, scholastic ability, and regional factors. Ogawa & Limura (2010) use the objective determinants to focus on family income and regional characteristics in line with the objectives of their study. Since it is costly and practically demanding to find data on all the variables and include them in the study, the approach used by Ogawa and Limura to focus on a few variables of interest is more feasible.

Given the objectives, the research questions, and the limitations in the data used for this study, this study adopts and modifies the conceptual framework used by Ogawa and Limura (2010). I use the objective determinants of access to higher education by focusing on household characteristics and community characteristics and add individual characteristics in the form of gender because several studies have found gender to be a significant determinant of access to education (Bowden & Doughney, 2012; Chakrabarti, 2009; Jansson et al., 2017; Sánchez & Singh, 2018). In this conceptual framework, I recognize that the factors that affect access to higher education also affect performance at the lower levels of education, such as primary and secondary education (Chevalier & Lanot, 2002; Farooq et al., 2011; Harmon & Walker, 2000; Tansel, 2002). Achievement and

attainment at lower levels of education in some way also affect access to higher education. To qualify for higher education, one ought to have passed secondary education in Uganda. So, factors that affect performance at the secondary level in a way affect the likelihood of qualifying for higher education. Primary education learning and performance also influence who goes to secondary education and consequently higher education.

Integrating the above concepts, the conceptual framework for this study shows that access to higher education is determined by individual characteristics like gender; Household socio-economic characteristics like household income, education level of the parents, number of siblings, age of the household head, etc.; and community characteristics like location, presence of schools, and access to the internet in the community etc. The above factors affect access to higher education directly but also affect achievement and attainment at lower levels of education which are necessary to proceed to higher education. Thus, indirectly, they affect access to higher education. The illustration below depicts the conceptual framework for this study.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework for the study

Source: Author's construct based on literature review.

Data and Descriptive statistics

1.1 Data

The study uses secondary data collected by the Uganda Bureau of Statistics (UBOS) for the 2016/17 Uganda National Household Survey (UNHS). The UNHS 2016/17 data is from the sixth edition of the Uganda National Household Survey. The exercise to collect this data was funded by the Uganda government, while the World Bank and UNICEF provided UBOS with technical assistance. The data is nationally representative, providing estimates for the whole country, including urban and rural areas and the four regions of Uganda. The sample is also representative of the fifteen sub-regions namely, West Nile, Acholi, Karamoja, Lango, Teso, Bunyoro, Elgon, Bukedi, Busoga, Central 1&2, Kigezi, Ankole, Kampala, and Toro. The 2016/17 UNHS used the 2014 list of enumeration areas from the National Population and Housing Census (NPHC) as the sample frame. The survey used a two-stage sampling design. In the first stage, 1750 enumeration areas were selected of which eighteen were not covered. In the second stage, ten households were randomly selected in each enumeration area (17320). The survey is rich in data concerning individual questions on education, income, health, and labour force; household-level questions on consumption expenditure, household assets, household enterprises, and market survey; and community-level questions on the availability of services, making the dataset suitable for use in this study.

Overall, the final sample had 3,422 complete observations after dropping all observations with incomplete data. In the sample, we only kept observations between the ages of 18 and 26 years because this is the age range when individuals in Uganda are expected to have entered or at least completed some level of higher education. The sample is also limited to individuals who have at least completed UCE. The reason is that only individuals who have completed UCE are eligible for higher education in Uganda as defined in this study. For the analysis, we followed the complete case analysis.

1.2 Variables

The study adopts higher education access as the outcome variable, which is a dummy variable that takes on the value of 1 for individuals who have completed or are currently enrolled in higher education studies. The unit of analysis is the individual.

Table 1: Description of Variables used in the study

Variable	Description	Hypothesis
Higher education	Dummy for whether one accessed higher education or not	N/A
Household head education	Number of years of schooling completed	+
Household head gender	Dummy for whether the household head is male	+
Household head age	Number of years of household head	+
Household size	Number of people living in a household.	-
Dependents	Number of children below eighteen years living in a household.	-
Household wealth	Wealth index scores are divided into five categories: one to five with five being the wealthiest and one the least wealthy or poorest.	+
Urban	The dummy variable for whether the household is in an urban area and 0 if the household is in a rural area.	+
Region	A categorical variable for four regions, namely, Central, Eastern, Northern, and Western.	+
Primary school:	Dummy for the presence of a primary school within the community.	+
Secondary school:	Dummy for the presence of a secondary school within the community.	+
Internet access:	Dummy for access to an internet point within the community	+
Gender:	Dummy for whether an individual is Male	+

Source: Author's construct

1.3 Description of the data

Table 2: The summary statistics of variables used in the study

Variable	Mean	S.D	Min	Max
Higher education (Yes=1)	0.19	0.39	0	1
Age	20.48	2.29	18	26
Gender (Male=1)	0.55	0.50	0	1
Urban (Yes=1)	0.41	0.49	0	1
Region	2.45	1.11	1	4
Gender of household head (Male=1)	0.65	0.48	0	1
Age Household head	49.80	9.12	36	65
Household head education	8.13	4.10	0	16
Household Wealth (1=lowest)	3.59	1.32	1	5
Household size	6.09	2.33	3	10
Dependents	2.88	2.21	0	11
Primary school (Yes=1)	0.64	0.48	0	1
Secondary school (yes=1)	0.25	0.43	0	1
Internet access (Yes=1)	0.51	0.50	0	1

Source: author's computation

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics of the data used in the study. The data shows that only 19% of the observations in the sample had accessed higher education. This is consistent with our expectation that a small percentage of Ugandans are enrolling for higher education. The average age of individuals in the sample is 20 years which is the age that students in Uganda are expected to have completed secondary education and have joined or are about to join tertiary education.

The average household size in the sample is six members, this is slightly more than the average household size reported in UBOS (2017). The number of dependents per household averaged three dependents. The average age for the household head is 49 years, and male-headed households dominate the sample at 69%.

Regarding the location of individuals, 43% of the individuals in the sample resided in urban areas while the majority, 57%, were in rural areas. In terms of accessing lower levels of education, most of the individuals in the study lived in a community where they could access a primary school, but only 25% of the individuals in the sample could access a secondary school within their community. As regards access to the internet within the community, 53% of the individuals in the study had internet access points.

Empirical Framework

1.4 Estimation technique

The empirical model is estimated using logistic regression as the estimation technique. The outcome variable being a binary outcome, I use logistic regression which is better equipped to handle such a problem. Logistic regression is superior to the linear probability model (LPM) which is susceptible to the unboundedness problem. Logistic regression solves this problem by mathematically transforming the original linear regression equation to yield the logit or natural log of the odds of being in one outcome category (Y^{\wedge}) versus the other category ($1 - Y^{\wedge}$). Logistic regression has another advantage in that it maintains many of the features of linear regression in its analysis of binary outcomes (Stoltzfus, 2011).

1.5 Empirical Model

To examine the determinants of access to higher education in Uganda, the study adopts a dummy variable, HE_{ij} , which takes on the value of 1 if the individual completed higher education or is currently enrolled in higher education and 0 otherwise. Because the dependent variable is binary, we estimate the model using logistic regression. We estimate the logistic model as follows:

$$prob(HE_{ij} = 1) = f(HH_{ij}, I_i, C_j)$$

Where HE_{ij} is the dependent variable in the model. $HE_{ij} = 1$ if individual i from household j completed or is currently enrolled in higher education; otherwise $HE_{ij} = 0$. HH_{ij} is a set of household socio-economic characteristics of household j from which individual i lives, I_i represents a set of individual characteristics of observation i , and C_j is a vector of community characteristics for where household j of individual i is located.

Results and Discussion

Table 3: Marginal effects of access to higher education after Logit regression.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
	Main	Males	Females	Urban	Rural
Age HH head	0.002*** (0.001)	0.003*** (0.001)	0.002* (0.001)	0.003*** (0.001)	0.002*** (0.001)
Gender HH head	-0.008 (0.016)	-0.014 (0.020)	-0.001 (0.024)	0.005 (0.026)	-0.020 (0.019)
Education HH head	0.015*** (0.002)	0.015*** (0.002)	0.016*** (0.003)	0.014*** (0.003)	0.015*** (0.002)
Dependents	-0.015*** (0.004)	-0.015*** (0.004)	-0.015** (0.006)	-0.035*** (0.007)	-0.003 (0.004)
Primary school	0.003 (0.016)	-0.011 (0.021)	0.020 (0.025)	0.024 (0.029)	-0.006 (0.019)
Secondary school	0.011 (0.016)	0.019 (0.019)	0.004 (0.023)	0.001 (0.025)	0.021 (0.020)
Internet access	0.034** (0.016)	0.029 (0.021)	0.037 (0.024)	0.040 (0.033)	0.029* (0.016)
Region					
Central	0.031 (0.021)	0.017 (0.026)	0.061* (0.034)	0.045 (0.035)	0.012 (0.028)
Eastern	0.018 (0.020)	-0.017 (0.027)	0.073** (0.035)	0.020 (0.039)	0.015 (0.024)
Western	0.053** (0.022)	0.024 (0.027)	0.098*** (0.035)	0.090** (0.041)	0.042* (0.024)
Wealth					
Low	0.070** (0.029)	0.092* (0.048)	0.088 (0.057)	0.012 (0.065)	0.158** (0.068)
Middle	0.059** (0.027)	0.072 (0.046)	0.087 (0.054)	0.039 (0.051)	0.148** (0.071)
High	0.063** (0.025)	0.088** (0.043)	0.071 (0.055)	0.095* (0.050)	0.111 (0.069)
Highest	0.130*** (0.025)	0.118*** (0.042)	0.177*** (0.052)	0.171*** (0.049)	0.171** (0.068)
Gender	-0.023* (0.013)			-0.014 (0.023)	-0.031** (0.015)
Urban	0.053*** (0.018)	0.059*** (0.021)	0.042* (0.026)		
<i>N</i>	3407	1853	1554	1457	1950

The dependent variable is access to higher education which is a dummy to indicate whether an individual has accessed higher education. The coefficients are presented as marginal effects with their corresponding robust standard errors in parentheses. Model 1 uses the entire sample, while models 2, 3, 4, and 5 use a sub-sample of the data based on urban/rural locations or female/male individuals. Models 2, 3, 4, and 5 present the determinants of access to higher education for males, females, and individuals from urban and rural areas respectively.

* p<0.10, ** p<0.05, *** p<0.01

The logistic regression results in **Table 4.1** reveal that, overall, there is a weakly significant effect of gender on an individual's access to higher education in Uganda. The coefficient for the gender of an individual is significant at the 10% level of significance (table 4.1, models 1 and 2). However, the direction of the effect is surprising. The results show that males are less likely to access higher education which contradicts findings from previous studies that showed males had an advantage in accessing higher education in Uganda. Earlier studies showed that being female had a negative influence on access to higher education in Uganda (Kwesiga, 1993; Mayanja, 1998), which was corroborated by relatively new evidence (Jansson et al., 2017).

Nevertheless, this finding is justifiable given that girls' education has been massively promoted in Uganda by civil society organizations (CSOs), non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and the government. For instance, the government of Uganda introduced an affirmative action policy of giving females 1.5 extra points when applying to join public universities. This resulted in the increased enrolment of females in higher education institutions (Alsan & Cutler, 2013; Odaga, 2020). The introduction of free universal primary education (UPE) in 1997 and universal secondary education (USE) in 2007 increased the enrolment of females in primary and secondary education. Admission into universal primary and secondary education is non-discriminative, giving males and females equal access to education. This has provided females/ girls with equal opportunity to access education as their male counterparts. As a result, both Gross Enrollment Ratio (GER) and Net Enrollment Ratio (NER) at primary and secondary levels show that there are more females enrolled at the respective levels of education than males (UNHS 2019/2020), which is evidence that females are accessing education and the massive promotion of girls' education is bearing results. This may partially explain why females are more likely to access higher education than males in Uganda.

Relatedly, in rural areas, males face significantly lower chances of accessing higher education than females. However, this may be due to the government of Uganda taking deliberate actions to promote girls' education such as The National Strategy for Girls Education in Uganda and the affirmative action that gave females preferential treatment in higher education like the extra 1.5 points awarded to females applying to join public universities. For instance, if a rural male and female student had equal points when applying to the same course at the same public university in Uganda, the female student through affirmative action would have greater chances of proceeding to higher education than the male student. Furthermore, males in urban areas also face reduced odds of accessing higher education albeit the coefficient is insignificant. This is suggestive of a creeping reversal in the effect of gender on accessing higher education in Uganda from what was observed in studies conducted two or three decades ago (Kwesiga, 1993; Mayanja, 1998). This finding needs to be investigated further and a more comprehensive study will help confirm if indeed there is an unnoticed reversal in the effect of gender on accessing higher education in Uganda.

Figure 2

The education level of the household head is significantly associated with an increase in the likelihood of an individual accessing higher education. In **Figure 2**, I observe that the effect of the education level of the household head is greater for individuals from urban areas than rural areas and for females compared to males. Educated household heads provide incentives, information, and opportunities for their children to attend higher education institutions. Education has intergenerational transmission effects that highly educated parents are more likely to have highly educated children (Ermisch Pronzato, 2010; Black et al., 2005).

The theory of possible selves postulates that individuals develop possible selves by comparing themselves to significant others in society (Harrison, 2018; Leondari, 1998; Markus & Nurius, 1986; Oyserman et al., 2004). So, it follows that individuals with more educated parents are likely to form possible selves that are favourable to attaining higher education because they are exposed to educated parents as role models. But also, from the perspective of the human capital theory, more educated parents are expected to have more income, thus they can invest in the education of their children compared to the less educated parents who are expected to have relatively less income. This finding is consistent with findings from other studies that have found parental

education to be a significant determinant of access to higher education. For example, Chakrabarti (2009); Finnie et al. (2005); Ogawa Iimura (2010); Sanchez Singh (2018) ;Vu et al. (2013).

Likewise, the age of the household head is a significant determinant of access to higher education. Individuals are more likely to access higher education if their household head is older. This may be because older household heads may on average be wealthier than their younger counterparts. After all, they have been working longer and accumulated more wealth. So, they have more resources to invest in their children's education. Whereas this finding contradicts Ogawa Iimura (2010) who found that the effect of the age of the household head is insignificant in determining access and equity to tertiary education in Indonesia, this finding closely corroborates the findings of Okumu et al. (2008) that found as a household head's age increases, the probability of a child dropping out of primary school reduces in Uganda. This suggests that the effect of the age of the household head on access to higher education may be contextual, and only effective in Uganda where Okumu et al. (2008) conducted a related study.

On the other hand, the gender of the household head is not a significant determinant of access to higher education. The coefficients on the gender of the household head are all insignificant in the results reported in Tables 4.1, 4.2, and Table 4.3. This study hypothesized that male-headed households were more likely to positively influence access to higher education compared to female-headed households. However, we find no significant influence of the gender of the household head on accessing higher education generally, and neither for individuals in rural or urban areas nor female or male groups. This finding contradicts Chakrabarti (2009) study which found that female-headed households, particularly in rural India, reduced the likelihood of attending higher education. Hence, holding other factors constant, the gender of the household head does not significantly shape whether one accesses higher education or not. From the human capital theory perspective, the decision to invest in education is based on the expected returns to education. So, it does not matter the gender of the household head if the household head can bear the costs of education and expect a positive return on investing in the education of their children, they will send the children to school.

The results show that the number of dependents in a household is associated with a reduced likelihood for individuals in that household to access higher education in Uganda. The effect is significant for both males and females and individuals in urban areas. Surprisingly, the effect is insignificant in rural areas. This is surprising because a majority of poor Ugandans reside in rural areas (UNHS, 2019/20), and we would expect an effect on accessing higher education for people in rural areas given the competition for limited resources in poor rural households. Theoretically, as the number of dependents increases, the likelihood of access to higher education reduces because there are fewer resources per capita available to support the education of all school-going children in the household. However, the finding that the number of dependents in rural households has no significant effect on their access to higher education in Uganda is consistent with what Ogawa and Iimura (2010) found in their study. They find that the chances of individuals in urban areas accessing tertiary education are more affected by the number of siblings/ dependents in the household than in rural areas. Therefore, the number of dependents/siblings may have a stronger

effect in urban areas than in rural areas. This may be because of the higher cost of living in urban areas as compared to rural areas which makes urban households resource-constrained and thus more responsive and sensitive to the costs of an additional dependent demanding education.

Generally, the finding that the more the number of dependents in a household the lower the chances of accessing higher education in Uganda is consistent with findings in other studies like Dang Rogers (2015), Ogawa Iimura (2010), Tomul Polat (2013). More dependents or siblings strain the available resources within the household to pay for education. The consequence is that all the children are given the same level of education which is less than they would have desired, or the parents are forced to choose within their children which ones to send to school given the available limited resources. Ultimately, affecting the chances of individuals accessing higher education.

Figure 3

Regarding wealth, the likelihood that an individual accesses higher education in Uganda tremendously increases as the household's wealth increases. In Figure 3, we observe that individuals in the highest, high, middle, and low wealth quintiles had a higher likelihood of accessing higher education as compared to those in the lowest quintile regardless of the gender of the individual. The effect of wealth is strongest for individuals in the highest and high-wealth quintiles, which represent the top two wealthiest groups in the sample. This finding is consistent

with findings from Chakrabarti (2009); Finnie et al. (2005); Ogawa Iimura (2010); Sanchez Singh (2018) where household wealth/income was found to be a key determinant of access to higher education.

Regarding location, living in urban areas significantly increases the likelihood of accessing higher education in Uganda. This is a reasonable finding since most higher education institutions are in urban or peri-urban areas which makes them easily accessible for individuals living in urban areas. We also see a positive and significant relationship between hailing from western Uganda, and access to higher education; people hailing from western Uganda have a higher likelihood of accessing higher education as compared to their counterparts from the northern region. We believe that the relative political stability that the Western region of Uganda enjoyed compared to the North could explain this finding. Political instability in the North affected both education and the ability of people to engage in productive economic activities, as a result, the region is one of the poorest in Uganda, which means many households cannot afford the costs of education. Also, for females, hailing from the north is detrimental to their chances of accessing higher education. We see that the likelihood of females from Western and Eastern Uganda accessing higher education is significantly higher in comparison to the Northern region.

Concerning access to the internet, individuals who have access to the internet within their communities have an increased likelihood of accessing higher education. The internet eases access to information on available academic programs, scholarships, and institutions to apply to. Also, the internet enables applying for higher education using online application portals. All these may explain why those who can access the internet are also more likely to access higher education compared to those without internet access.

Finally, there is no significant effect of the presence of a primary or secondary school on access to higher education. With the introduction of universal primary and secondary education, individuals can easily move to nearby communities for schooling if their community does not have a primary or secondary school. This may explain why the presence of a primary or secondary school has no significant effect on access to higher education.

Summary and concluding remarks

1.6 Summary

Higher education is instrumental for the social and economic development of society, and access to higher education is likely to become rapidly more important for developing countries like Uganda as they look to transform their economies. However, despite its relevance, determinants of access to higher education are still understudied in the Ugandan context. This study has contributed to addressing the gaps in the literature by presenting a nationally representative cross-sectional analysis of factors determining access to higher education in Uganda. Using the 2016/17 UNHS dataset, this study finds that the education level of the household head, household wealth, and location are key determinants of access to higher education in Uganda. The study also finds a strong influence of internet access and the age of the household head on access to higher education in Uganda. Contrary to earlier studies, the study does find that males are less likely to access higher

education than females, especially in rural areas. Additionally, the presence of a primary or secondary school in the community does not seem to have a significant effect on the likelihood of accessing higher education for individuals within that community.

1.7 Concluding Remarks

This study explores the determinants of access to higher education in Uganda using a nationally representative dataset. The results revealed that socioeconomic factors like household wealth, education level of the household head, location, and number of dependents in the household are key determinants of access to higher education in Uganda. The results show that gender is a weak determinant of access to higher education in Uganda, and contrary to earlier studies, I find that males are less likely to access higher education compared to females, especially in rural areas.

This study had several limitations. For example, the UNHS 2016-17 dataset lacked data on some key variables of interest for this study like the education level of both parents for each observation. Including the educational level of both the father and mother in the analysis would have enabled us to disaggregate the effect of parental education on access to higher education. The education level of the household head which we use as a proxy for parental education is not perfect because the household head may not necessarily be the biological parent of the individual we are observing. Also, the dataset lacked individual academic grades for UCE and UACE that we would ideally have used as controls for academic ability in our regressions. Grades are a key consideration in admitting students to higher education institutions.

Future research should extend this analysis by incorporating variables on parental education and academic grades. Also, further research should deeply explore the likely reversal of the effect of gender on access to higher education in Uganda. Further research on the possible reversal of the effect of gender on access to higher education in Uganda is of policy relevance. The government of Uganda adopted affirmative action and the national girl's education strategy to promote female education. The question is have these strategies resulted in overly promoting female education at the expense of males, especially in rural areas?

References

- Alsan, M. M., & Cutler, D. M. (2013). Girls' education and HIV risk: Evidence from Uganda. *Journal of Health Economics*, 32(5), 863–872. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhealeco.2013.06.002>
- Bowden, M. P., & Doughney, J. (2012). The importance of cultural and economic influences behind the decision to attend higher education. *The Journal of Socio-Economics*, 41(1), 95–103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socec.2011.10.003>
- Brennan, J., Durazzi, N., & Séné, T. (2013, October). *Things we know and don't know about the wider benefits of higher education: A review of the recent literature* (Monograph URN BIS/13/1244). Department for Business, Innovation and Skills. <https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/department-for-business-innovation-skills>
- Breton, T. R. (2013). The role of education in economic growth: Theory, history and current returns. *Educational Research*, 55(2), 121–138. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131881.2013.801241>
- Chakrabarti, A. (2009). Determinants of Participation in Higher Education and Choice of Disciplines: Evidence from Urban and Rural Indian Youth. *South Asia Economic Journal*, 10(2), 371–402. <https://doi.org/10.1177/139156140901000205>
- Chevalier, A., & Lanot, G. (2002). The Relative Effect of Family Characteristics and Financial Situation on Educational Achievement. *Education Economics*, 10(2), 165–181. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09645290210126904>
- Farooq, M. S., Chaudhry, A. H., Shafiq, M., & Berhanu, G. (2011). *FACTORS AFFECTING STUDENTS' QUALITY OF ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE: A CASE OF SECONDARY SCHOOL LEVEL*. 15.
- Harmon, C., & Walker, I. (2000). The Returns to the Quantity and Quality of Education: Evidence for Men in England and Wales. *Economica*, 67(265), 19–35. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-0335.00193>
- Harrison, N. (2018). Using the Lens of 'Possible Selves' to Explore Access to Higher Education: A New Conceptual Model for Practice, Policy, and Research. *Social Sciences*, 7(10), 209. <https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci7100209>
- Holmes, C. (2013). Has the Expansion of Higher Education Led to Greater Economic Growth? *National Institute Economic Review*, 224, R29–R47. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002795011322400103>

- Jacob, W. J., Nsubuga, Y. K., & Mugimu, C. B. (2009). Higher Education in Uganda: The Role of Community Colleges in Educational Delivery and Reform. In R. L. Raby & E. J. Valeau (Eds.), *Community College Models* (pp. 335–358). Springer Netherlands. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-9477-4_19
- Jansson, B., Bukuluki, P., & Hojer, S. (2017). Higher education in Uganda: Gender, socio-economic status, geographical background and sponsorship in a group of social work students at Makerere University. *International Social Work*, *60*(6), 1370–1386. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020872817710544>
- Jimenez, J., & Salas-velasco. (2000). *Modeling educational choices. A binomial logit model applied to the demand for Higher Education*. 20.
- Kwesiga, J. C. (1993). Access of women to higher education in Uganda: An analysis of inequalities, barriers and determinants. [Doctoral, Institute of Education, University of London]. In *Doctoral thesis, Institute of Education, University of London*. <https://discovery.ucl.ac.uk/id/eprint/10006581/>
- Leondari, A. et al. (1998). *Academic achievement, motivation and possible selves*. 5.
- Markus, H., & Nurius, P. (1986). Possible selves. *American Psychologist*, *41*(9), 954–969. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.41.9.954>
- Mayanja, M. K. (1998). The social background of Makerere University students and the potential for cost sharing. *Higher Education*, *36*(1), 21–41. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1003238928267>
- McMahon, W. W. (2018). The total return to higher education: Is there underinvestment for economic growth and development? *The Quarterly Review of Economics and Finance*, *70*, 90–111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.qref.2018.05.005>
- McMahon, W. W. (2021). *The External Social Benefits of Higher Education: Theory, Evidence, and Policy Implications*. 18.
- McMahon, W. W., & Oketch, M. (2013). Education's Effects on Individual Life Chances and On Development: An Overview. *British Journal of Educational Studies*, *61*(1), 79–107. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00071005.2012.756170>
- Nshemereirwe, C. V. (2016). *SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS AND ACCESS TO HIGHER EDUCATION IN UGANDA*. 1, 13.
- Odaga, G. (2020). Gender in Uganda's tertiary educational distribution. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, *2*(1), 100023. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2020.100023>

Ogawa, K., & Iimura, K. (2010). Determinants of Access and Equity in Tertiary Education: The Case of Indonesia. *Excellence in Higher Education*, 1, 20.

Okumu, Alex, Nakajjo, & Doreen, Isoke. (2008). *Socioeconomic determinants of primary school dropout: The logistic model analysis*. <https://core.ac.uk/reader/6372700>

Oyserman, D., Bybee, D., Terry, K., & Hart-Johnson, T. (2004). Possible selves as roadmaps. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 38(2), 130–149. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0092-6566\(03\)00057-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0092-6566(03)00057-6)

Peet, E. D., Fink, G., & Fawzi, W. (2015). Returns to education in developing countries: Evidence from the living standards and measurement study surveys. *Economics of Education Review*, 49, 69–90. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econedurev.2015.08.002>

Psacharopoulos, G., & Patrinos, H. A. (2004). Returns to investment in education: A further update. *Education Economics*, 12(2), 111–134. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0964529042000239140>

Sánchez, A., & Singh, A. (2018). Accessing higher education in developing countries: Panel data analysis from India, Peru, and Vietnam. *World Development*, 109, 261–278. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2018.04.015>

Stoltzfus, J. C. (2011). Logistic Regression: A Brief Primer: LOGISTIC REGRESSION: A BRIEF PRIMER. *Academic Emergency Medicine*, 18(10), 1099–1104. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1553-2712.2011.01185.x>

Tansel, A. (2002). Determinants of school attainment of boys and girls in Turkey: Individual, household and community factors. *Economics of Education Review*, 21(5), 455–470. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0272-7757\(01\)00028-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0272-7757(01)00028-0)

Tomul, E., & Polat, G. (2013). The Effects of Socioeconomic Characteristics of Students on Their Academic Achievement in Higher Education. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 1(10), 449–455. <https://doi.org/10.12691/education-1-10-7>

Uganda Bureau of Statistics - UBOS & ICF. (2018). Uganda Demographic and Health Survey 2016. UBOS and ICF. <http://dhsprogram.com/pubs/pdf/FR333/FR333.pdf>

Uganda Bureau of Statistics (UBOS), 2021. Uganda National Household Survey 2019/2020. Kampala, Uganda; UBOS.

Uganda Bureau of Statistics. (2017). The national population and housing census 2014 – education

in the thematic report series.

UN General Assembly. (2015). Transforming our world: The 2030 agenda for sustainable development. <https://www.refworld.org/docid/57b6e3e44.htm>

